

Development of a Pelvic Model for Study of Surgical Errors in the Midurethral Sling Procedure

¹Md A. Arif, ²Fizza Mahmud, ¹Gregory W. King, ²Gary Sutkin, ¹Antonis P. Stylianou

¹Department of Civil & Mechanical Engineering, University of Missouri – Kansas City, MO, USA

²Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, University of Missouri – Kansas City, MO, USA

Email: maa5g8@mail.umkc.edu, web: <http://s.web.umkc.edu/stylianou/>

INTRODUCTION

Surgical procedures always involve an element of risk and even a minor error can lead to serious complications. Recent data suggests that over 200 million surgeries are performed annually worldwide and about 3 to 22% of these surgeries involve some sort of complications. Surgical errors can be caused by both technical errors and cognitive errors which may happen to even an experienced surgeon. However, resident surgeons are more prone to surgical errors as they start their surgical career with less experience and skills [1]. In order to reduce errors and accelerate the learning experience of surgeons, we propose a method that can identify, model and prevent surgical errors by using biomechanical motion analysis and a high-fidelity 3-D surgery simulator.

Our work targets a complex, common, and high-risk surgery for stress urinary incontinence called the midurethral sling (MUS) procedure. The procedure involves using a sharp steel trocar to place a mesh underneath the urethra to control its mobility. For this surgery, the surgeon has to guide the sharp steel trocar blindly past the bladder, bowel and some major blood vessels that require the surgeon to have distinct surgical skills (bimanual dexterity, ability to envision a blind 3-D space, strong knowledge on the complex anatomy of the periurethral and perivesical spaces etc.) [2].

Surgical errors occurring during trocar passage procedure could be described and therefore predicted and/or prevented by discrete changes in the kinematics of the surgeon's shoulder, arm, hand and the spatio-temporal characteristics of the trocar [3]. The main goal of this study is to create a high fidelity 3-D pelvic simulator to study the kinematics of on particular high-risk step of the MUS surgery.

METHODS

The first step in this work is to create a high fidelity 3-D model of the pelvic anatomy. The Virtual Pelvic Surgery model (VPS) was developed from segmentation of high resolution magnetic resonance images (MRI) of a 57-year-old female patient with stress urinary incontinence. Structures of pelvic anatomy including bone, muscle, blood vessels, bladder, uterus, urethra, vaginal wall, and skin were segmented from MRI using 3D Slicer (www.slicer.org). The 3-D geometries were post-processed using MeshLab (<http://www.meshlab.net/>) and Artec Studio (www.artec3d.com). Post-processing of 3-D geometries included reduction of artifacts and noise, and decimation to reduce the file sizes. Finally, all individual geometries were combined to form the complete 3-D virtual pelvis model.

The VPS was then used to construct a physical pelvic model. All the structures of the pelvic anatomy were 3-D printed using a Dimension bst1200es series 3D printer. Individual physical structures are assembled and encased to construct the complete 3-D physical pelvis model.

The next step will be to use biomechanical motion analysis (www.vicon.com) to measure surgeon shoulder, hand, and arm kinematics, as well as the kinematics of the surgical instrument during simulated trocar passages. The kinematics of the most common surgical errors (injury of the bladder, urethra, bowel, or external iliac vessels) will be analyzed using this procedure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

High resolution T2 MR Image sequences were used to segment the bowel, urethra, vaginal wall, ureter,

levator muscle and rectus abdominus muscles. Muscles such as obturator, quad, vastus, adductor, tensor fasciae latae, sartorius, iliopsoas, rectus femoris, piriformis, pectineus, gracilis, semimembranosus and semitendinosus were more clearly visible from out-phase MR image sequences. In-Phase MR image sequences were used to segment the skin (with fat layer), part of bowel and urethra. Major blood vessels (external iliac vein and artery, femoral vein and artery), fascia and bowel were segmented from the Water MR Image sequences. Femur, pelvic bone, bladder, rectum and uterus were segmented from all five sequences (T2, In-Phase, Out-Phase, Water and Fiesta) and merged to finalize these geometries.

Figure 1: Pelvic Model (after post-processing)

High resolution Out-Phase MR image sequences have been used to extract the peritoneum membrane to provide us with a proper indicator of surgeon's performance. In ideal cases, it is expected that the surgeon will maintain minimum distance between the trocar and peritoneum membrane while performing this surgery.

Figure 2: Pelvic Model with Peritoneum

Figure 3: Virtual CAD model with mid-plates

During the procedure, the trocar will never cross through the mid-plane of the pelvic anatomy. This novel model includes two thin plates (3mm thickness) in the middle to attach the soft tissues and blood vessels from both sides, and two mid-plates have been mounted on each other using 8 small posts (3mm radius for each of them). After post-processing, small posts and pockets (5mm radius) have been created on individual geometries using FreeCAD (www.freecad.com) to attach them on the physical model based on correct anatomical orientation.

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this research project is to create a realistic anatomical platform on which surgical trainees can practice their skills and get effective feedback on their overall surgical errors through kinematic analysis.

REFERENCES

1. WHO Guidelines for Safe Surgery 2009: Safe Surgery Safe Lives. 2009, World Health Organization: Geneva.
2. Ford et al., Mid-urethral sling for stress urinary incontinence. Cochrane Database, 2015
3. Siddicky, S., Use of Biomechanical Motion Analysis to Evaluate Endotracheal Intubation Skill, UMKC, 2015

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

University of Missouri Research Board (UMRB)

(IRB Protocol ID: 17-310; PI: Gary Sutkin, M.D.)